

Some Considerations on the Scientific Production of Agrotourism from 1991 To 2023

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to describe the trends and current state of agritourism and the role of agritourism farms within it, based on a bibliometric study from its beginnings up to the year 2023. The source of information used was the Scopus Database. Theoretical methods such as analysis-synthesis and historical-logical approaches were employed, along with empirical methods including scientific observation, unstructured interviews, and the triangulation of sources and methods. Altogether, these allowed the identification of trends, regularities, and relationships in the phenomenon under study, based on the information obtained during the research process, as well as the formulation of conclusions. As a result, the foundations were established for further theoretical and practical exploration of the topic through the analysis of bibliometric indicators. From a population of 101 journals publishing on tourism management across various scientific fields, only 287 articles on agritourism were found, of which seven focused specifically on agritourism farms. In addition, a general overview of the subject was established, and the behavior of scientific production on agritourism from its origins to 2023 was described. Consequently, the insufficient analysis of agritourism farms as a distinctive element of this tourism modality and their contribution to territorial development was evidenced. The findings of this research provide a scientific basis to support strategic decision-making that links both the agricultural and tourism sectors in favor of territorial development.

Keywords

agrotourism; agrotourism farms; scientific production; bibliometric indicators

I. Introduction

Agrotourism emerges as an alternative to generate higher income in localities primarily dedicated to economic activities related to agriculture and livestock. Therefore, it has been considered an opportunity to increase income, reduce poverty, and diminish socioeconomic inequalities between urban and rural areas. In fact, it has become a guiding axis of public policies and has been fully integrated in certain contexts, where it is regarded as an instrument for multifunctionality and economic diversification (Anzardo et al., 2022; Guerra & González, 2019; Oe & Yamaoka, 2021; Pérez & Cardet, 2022; Pérez Anzardo et al., 2023, 2025; Rodríguez, 2019).

This tourism modality began in the second half of the 20th century as a driving force for territorial development in several countries, aiming to diversify their economies based on their own potential. Likewise, it is considered a specialized segment of rural tourism, and therefore a variant linked to alternative, environmental, nature-based, and social tourism, which is mainly developed on farms (Ledhesma, 2018). Its purpose is to satisfy specific market segments that are environmentally committed, with an interest focused on learning about rural culture (Acevedo, 2022; Anzardo et al., 2023; Noa & Gascón, 2023; Oe & Yamaoka, 2021; Rodríguez, 2019; Weeks et al., 2021).

An opportunity to be seized is that current tourism markets coincide with the main issuers of alternative tourism at the international level; this requires an exhaustive study of trends related to the design of offers aimed at satisfying demand and contributing to territorial development (Pérez & Cardet, 2022). In this regard, the globally recognized guiding document is the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, declared by the United Nations in September 2015. Several of its 17 goals and 169 targets support the linkage between the agricultural and tourism sectors, so that policies and instruments are responsibly implemented to create jobs, generate income, and promote the culture of local products, with a transformative vision toward economic, social, and environmental sustainability (UNWTO, 2018).

In Cuba, to respond to the strategies adopted by the UN, the National Plan for Economic and Social Development 2030 (PNDES) was approved at the 7th Congress of the Communist Party of Cuba in 2017. Among its main objectives is to promote socioeconomic development according to the characteristics of each territory. In addition, it seeks to strengthen the articulation between agriculture and tourism to increase export revenues, generate employment opportunities, promote national and local culture, and enhance linkages with domestic markets and national production. Hence, the importance of proper knowledge management regarding existing theoretical gaps that limit the development of agritourism, based on strategic alliances between the sectors involved.

Although the culture of marketing sustainable agriculture in Cuba—a predominantly agricultural country—is relatively new, it does not correspond to the way agritourism is managed in other countries that have made progress in this regard. These activities are generally carried out by farm owners in isolation, which hinders the diversity of the offer aimed at satisfying customers and generating higher income that contributes to the development of rural communities (Moral et al., 2019; Pérez & Cardet, 2022; Rodríguez, 2019).

As Ramírez et al. (2020) point out, research on agritourism farms has slowed due to the limited identification of natural assets and agro-productive activities for tourism purposes. Its conceptual treatment presents divergences between the Latin American context and the rest of the world, influenced by internal and external factors, as well as macroeconomic variables rather than the inherent characteristics of this entity, in such a way that an economic response to local social problems can be guaranteed (Alcalá & López, 2017; Cevallos, 2021; Muñoz & Zambrano, 2021; Noboa, 2019; Saldaña, 2016).

Consequently, the purpose of this research is to deepen the study of trends and the state of the art of the subject under analysis from its beginnings until 2023. To this end, the bibliometric analysis of agritourism and the role of agritourism farms in its management allows, through metric indicators, the visualization of its behavior as an outstanding economic activity within the agricultural sector and as a governmental policy that promotes territorial development. Furthermore, it facilitates the realization of quantitative studies and the formulation of forecasts for timely decision-making. In this way, improvement actions can be implemented that, with the participation of academia, contribute to territorial development and the growth of the sectors involved (Gontijo et al., 2021).

Its novelty lies in contributing from science to better agritourism management due to its economic, social, and environmental utility when properly implemented. In addition, it provides the scientific community with a tool that serves as a basis for future research. Likewise, it offers entrepreneurs the possibility of implementing local development projects and diversifying agricultural businesses that incorporate peasant traditions, which will foster the growth of family and community economies. It promotes social regeneration

in harmony with the environment in favor of territorial development anywhere in the world.

II. Research Methods

For the development of this research, the specialized Scopus Database was used, considered the largest source of abstracts and citations of peer reviewed literature and available on high quality websites, as it contains around 18,000 titles from 5,000 publishers worldwide. Through this database, bibliometric indicators of scientific production on agritourism were obtained for the period between 1991 and 2023.

The study population encompassed 101 journals across 20 sources that publish topics related to tourism management. The analysis included 287 articles addressing the subject from 1991 onward in various scientific fields, representing 100% of the total records up to 2023. These comprised scientific articles, conference papers, books, book chapters, editorial material, and review articles. Selection criteria were established, such as scientific production by country, annual output, most productive scientific areas, most relevant authors, trends in topics related to agritourism, and the use of key variables, among others. In addition, both theoretical and empirical research methods were combined, which allowed the identification of trends and the establishment of relationships with agritourism based on the information obtained during the research process. The results were presented using descriptive statistics in the form of graphs and tables. Thus, the study adopted a quantitative, descriptive, non experimental approach, which enabled the formulation of conclusions.

III. Result and Discussion

The results obtained through data processing, based on bibliometric indicators and the analysis of scientific literature at both international and national levels on agritourism, confirmed that the most prominent countries in scientific production are located in the Eurasian continent: Indonesia (66), Greece (23), Russian Federation (22), Poland (21), Romania (14), Spain (11), Thailand (10), Croatia (9), Malaysia (9), and the Czech Republic (8). This highlights the limited collaboration on the subject from the rest of the world, as shown in Figures 1 and 2. Moreover, in this database, the visibility of research conducted in Latin America, the Caribbean, and Cuba is nonexistent, despite the fact that studies on the topic with practical applications have been developed

Figure 1: Map of country collaboration in the scientific production of agritourism

Figure 2: Scientific production by country

Figure 3 shows an increase in publications beginning in 2015, with an annual average of 10 documents. Later, in 2021, the maximum level of agritourism production was reached, with approximately 38 documents.

Figure 3: Annual scientific production on agritourism

With regard to the most prominent authors, Figure 4 shows that Mulyo JH contributed five articles, Jamhari four, and Iakovidou O, Indrayanti T, Kizos T, and Masyhuri three each, among others. Likewise, Figure 5 reflects the yearly overlap of these researchers.

Figure 4: Most relevant authors

Figure 5: Author overlap in relation to agritourism

In turn, among the sources that most contributed to the visibility of scientific production on agritourism are those shown in Figure 6. These include conferences on land and environment, business and economics; online conferences; and journals on environmental management and tourism.

Figure 6: Most significant sources in the scientific production of agritourism

One of the most well-known bibliometric indicators is the impact factor, which evaluates the number of citations to articles published in a journal over the previous two years, divided by the number of citable documents published by the journal in the same period. In this case, the most prominent sources were the African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure; online conferences; conferences on land and environmental sciences; and the Central European Journal of Agriculture, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Impact source according to the h-index

Likewise, the average number of articles cited per year is shown in Figure 8, where it is reflected that the highest peak was reached in the period from 2001 to 2003, with more than four articles

Figure 8: Average number of articles cited per year

All these documents were presented across various areas of scientific knowledge, as shown in the pie chart in Figure 9. Among the most significant are the social sciences and environmental sciences, with 19.3%, which demonstrates the impact of agritourism on sustainable territorial development in economic, social, and environmental dimensions. In this line of thought, it is essential to understand the degree of relevance of agritourism farms as a distinctive element of this tourism modality, since, as López-González et al. (2016) affirm, the main variables of sustainability lie in agricultural activity.

Figure 9: Areas of science with the highest number of publications on agritourism

At first, the concept of agritourism was associated with tourism and rural development; later, it was enriched with the notion of sustainable development. Figures 10 and 11 show the trend in the use of variables associated with agritourism, as well as their degree of relevance and development. Initially, the concept of agritourism was linked to tourism and rural development, and subsequently expanded to include sustainable development.

Figure 10: Trend in the use of variables associated with agritourism

Figure 11: Relevance and development of agritourism variables

Regarding the most frequently used words associated with agritourism, the most common are tourism, followed by agriculture, rural development, rural area, and sustainable development, as shown in Figures 12 and 13. However, the use of the independent variable “agritourism farm” does not stand out among the most relevant

Figure 15: Tree of relevant agritourism variables expressed in percentages

Finally, the analysis of scientific production and the bibliometric study developed on agritourism made it possible to align with the criteria presented by the authors studied and to delimit the differences regarding the evaluation of agritourism farms as a distinctive support of this modality. Agritourism is an emerging activity that strengthens the economy through rural and agricultural practices carried out by small entrepreneurs. Hence, there is a need to persuade both the academic community and local managers to promote agritourism with a forward-looking approach.

Therefore, proper planning is indispensable to avoid deteriorating or even exhausting its own resource base through public policies and actions by the managers involved. It constitutes a form of alternative tourism that is gaining increasing support worldwide, for which Cuba has broad possibilities for implementation. In its holistic nature, it is influenced by internal and external elements that determine its management and impact on sustainable territorial development, which have been studied according to the areas of knowledge and contexts in which the concept has been addressed.

IV. Conclusions

1. Through the bibliometric study carried out on agritourism and the incidence of agritourism farms, it was possible to identify global scientific production from its visibility across various areas of scientific knowledge between 1991 and 2023.
2. Author productivity is low, and the most prominent countries are located in the Eurasian continent, although in the Americas articles with practical applications are also developed, yet they remain scarcely recognized in the most prestigious databases.
3. The bibliometric study makes it possible to visualize the behavior and trends of agritourism and the variables associated with it, as an outstanding element of the agricultural sector closely linked to tourism, and as a strategy that, through government policies, fosters sustainable territorial development in economic, social, and environmental dimensions.
4. From the reflection carried out in this study on the behavior and trends of agritourism, it is demonstrated that agritourism, as a prominent framework of the agricultural sector and as a governmental policy, allows diversification of agricultural business offerings, as well as social regeneration in harmony with the environment worldwide.
5. Farms with agritourism potential make the difference between agritourism and other forms of alternative tourism. Hence, it is important to analyze the elements that hinder their prospective development, since, based on public policies, they contribute to a prosperous economy founded on knowledge and innovation, competitive and

environmentally friendly. This mitigates inequalities between rural and urban areas and represents an opportunity to contribute to sustainable territorial development.

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